

**Territory, senses, and emotions:
transdisciplinary case of the university campus**

*Territorio, sentidos y emociones: caso transdisciplinario
del campus universitario*

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Abstract

This research examines how emotional and sensory experiences related to natural and urban spaces within the university campus help cultivate a transdisciplinary perspective aimed at fostering responsive and inclusive communities. Using qualitative methods, this study employs a phenomenological and ethnographic sensory approach through a multiple-case study design. Interpretation is based on methodological bricolage using diverse theoretical perspectives and data collection tools. The process is organized into five phases, and through axial coding, 40 dimensions were identified from a model of knowledge dialogue constructed by the senses. Through grounded theory, a conceptual and systematic cartography of the posthuman phenomenon is presented, articulated in: explanatory theories on sensitivity, gender, urban planning, and inclusive politics (based on a posphenomenological approach); constructed from a body, a territory, and situated educational practices. The study concludes with theoretical and methodological contributions and educational implications, allowing us to address the relevance of the “philosophical quantum” for teacher training. The role of the teacher-researcher in the creation of knowledge is highlighted, as well as the impact of recognizing the territory and contexts where educational experiences are developed through transformative teaching.

Keywords

Teaching skills, data analysis, educational environment, cultural conditions, social science policy, human behavior, emotions.

Resumen

Esta investigación examina cómo las experiencias emocionales y sensoriales en relación con los espacios naturales y urbanos dentro del campus universitario ayudan a cultivar una perspectiva transdisciplinaria destinada a fomentar comunidades sensibles e inclusivas. Utilizando métodos cualitativos, este estudio emplea un enfoque fenomenológico y etnográfico sensorial a través de un diseño de estudio de casos múltiples. La interpretación se basa en el bricolaje metodológico utilizando diversas perspectivas teóricas y herramientas para la recolección de datos. El proceso está organizado en cinco fases, y a través de la codificación axial se identificaron 40 dimensiones que forman un modelo de diálogo de conocimiento construido por los sentidos. A través de la teoría fundamentada se presenta una cartografía conceptual y sistemática del fenómeno poshumano, articuladas en: teorías explicativas sobre sensibilidad, género, urbanismo y política inclusiva (a partir de un enfoque posfenomenológico); construida a partir de un cuerpo, un territorio y prácticas educativas situadas. Se concluye con los aportes teóricos, metodológicos e implicaciones educativas, permitiendo abordar la relevancia del “quantum filosófico” para la formación docente. Se resalta el papel del profesor-investigador en la creación del saber, así como el impacto que tiene el reconocer el territorio y los contextos donde se desarrollan las experiencias educativas desde la enseñanza transformadora.

Palabras clave

Habilidad pedagógica, análisis de datos, ambiente educacional, condiciones culturales, política de las ciencias sociales, comportamiento, afectividad.

Introduction

The sensory or affective orientation in the social sciences and humanities facilitates the understanding of knowledge emanating from emotional communities through theoretical-methodological models and analytical vocabularies based on poststructuralist thinking. This perspective has revolutionized fields such as anthropology, sociology, history, and cultural studies by questioning conventional knowledge frameworks and introducing new ways of interpreting reality, language, power, and subjectivity (Howes, 2013, 2014; López-Sánchez, 2023; Turner, 2009).

Under this approach, the figure of *the bricoleur*, proposed by Denzin and Lincoln (2012) and reinterpreted by the Chicago School (Jiménez and Cisneros, 2025), takes importance. This category of scholar uses a variety of methods and theories to examine complex phenomena, incorporating varied approaches depending on the resources available. Metaphorically, they are also known as *quilt makers*, alluding to individuals who integrate fragments of knowledge into a complete piece (Denzin and Lincoln, 2012, p. 12).

Sensory perception, conceptualized as a physically and cerebrally mediated sociocultural process, is also established in interpersonal interactions, where affective and control dynamics develop. The exploration of the sensory faculties of sight, hearing, touch, taste, and smell in everyday life challenges the rationalist paradigm of scientific knowledge, integrating emotions as essential components in the construction of meanings, social practices, and subjectivities (Castro, 2014; Castro-Gómez, 2010; Deleuze, 2015; Dreyfus and Rabinow, 2001; Eribon, 1995; Jambet, 1999; Morey, 2014).

This study examines how sensory and emotional experiences, in interaction with the natural and urban space of the university campus, contribute to a transdisciplinary perspective with the aim of building inclusive and responsive communities. The research focuses on three fundamental questions:

1. How do emotional and sensory communities influence the development of a transdisciplinary perspective in the university setting?
2. What are the interrelationships between the natural and urban environment, emotions, and the senses in the academic context?
3. How does the administration of audiences in the university environment promote social participation and the formation of sensitive and inclusive communities?

From a phenomenological and ethnographic-sensory perspective (Stake, 2000), dimensions of university life are recognized from the perspective of faculty, with consequences for the optimization of institutional policies, spaces of coexistence, and inclusive practices. In addition, the role of university outreach in the formation of social connections through effective and sensory practices is investigated.

According to Ahmed (2015), collective emotions play a crucial role in the formation of emotional communities, as they facilitate the mobilization of individuals toward shared goals. Simultaneously, the term sensory community refers to a collective perception that manifests itself when the senses amalgamate around a social phenomenon, enabling transformative actions based on experience.

For Turner (2009), emotions manifest themselves at various levels: biological, behavioral, cultural, and structural, so their definition is conditioned by the theoretical approach adopted. From a neurological, cultural, or cognitive perspective, emotions manifest themselves through bodily activations, social norms, or conscious feelings.

Since the 1970s, authors such as Collins (1975), Heise (1979), Hochschild (1975, 1979), Kemper (1978a, 1978b), and Scheff (1979) have promoted theories about emotions, contributing progressively to the expansion of this field. During the 1980s, Williams (1977) and Hall (1980) emphasized culture as an experienced practice, while Surrallés (1998) explored the emotional dimension of indigenous cultures from the perspective of kinship systems.

In the 1990s, affect theory gained prominence thanks to writers such as Massumi (1995) and Deleuze and Guattari (1987), who stated that affects are preconscious forces that establish connections between bodies and spaces. At the dawn of the 21st century, perspectives such as sensory anthropology (Howes, 2003; Pink, 2009) emerged, focusing on embodied experience and the use of technologies to document and represent such experiences. Pink (2015) proposes a forward-looking ethnography that examines how individuals experience, conceive, and shape future worlds.

Currently, sensory cultural research (Bourdin, 2016; Bolaños, 2015; Fernández, 2011) is dedicated to investigating the bodily, emotional, and artistic experiences of indigenous peoples, community actors, study or research groups, as well as educational institutions at different levels. In Mexico, Báez (2023) examines regional identity through the use of sounds in Central America, while Martínez (2023) analyzes streets as “non-places,” spaces of tran-

sit and identity in contemporary cities. For socio-educational environments, Jiménez-León *et al.* (2024) compiles the discursive phenomenon from academic actors in training, and Mateos-Cortés (2025) specifies transdisciplinary creative positions in intergroup and intercultural processes from Latin American geographical coordinates.

Materials and method

This study adopted a qualitative methodological approach (Denzin and Lincoln, 1998), driven by the desire to understand how sensory and emotional experiences in university environments shape new forms of academic interaction, territorial identity, and transdisciplinary knowledge construction. This methodological journey was divided into five interconnected phases (see Figure 1) that allowed for the integration of theory, field experience, analysis, and interpretation from a perspective sensitive to the environment and educational actors, which are described below.

The first phase was a theoretical and contextual review that laid the conceptual foundations for the study. Through a critical reading of the specialized literature, key contributions on the cultural construction of the senses (Geurts, 2002), the role of emotions in everyday life (Stewart, 2007), and the multiple ways of observing and recording social reality (Guber, 2011) were explored. Elements related to the historicity of sensory perceptions (Corbin, 2005), the use of audiovisual media as epistemic tools (Pink, 2015), and perspectives from sensory anthropology in contemporary contexts (Howes, 2024) were also included. This phase not only provided a solid theoretical framework but also helped define the key dimensions to be observed in the fieldwork.

In the second phase, the study moved to the field. A sensory-ethnographic observation protocol was created that allowed recording subjective experiences on the university campus from a visual, auditory, and emotional perspective. The methodology used a mix of techniques, such as participant observation, audio collection, participatory photography, field shorthand, and the use of digital applications. The geographical context of the study at the Faculty of Education of the Autonomous University of Yucatán provided a unique environment because it was in a natural ecosystem and its architectural design was oriented towards integrating learning with the environment. The triangulation of techniques, the intentional selection of significant cases, and the

ethical adherence to the principles of informed consent helped to ensure the validity and reliability of the work.

Figure 1

Qualitative research approach, through a phenomenological and sensory ethnographic study in multiple case studies

The third phase was the analysis of the collected data. A corpus including narratives, images, and sound recordings was used to carry out an open, axial, and inductive coding process (Schreier, 2012; Kuckartz & Rädiker, 2023). This process resulted in more than twenty thousand initial codes, of which 243 were refined with 40 central dimensions being chosen for the study. The analysis was divided into three levels: micro (individual experiences), meso (institutional dynamics), and macro (sociocultural frameworks). This allowed for an understanding of university life from a sensitive, situated, and relational point of view.

Multiple case study became the main methodological strategy in the fourth phase (Stake, 2000). The first case analyzed how the natural environment of the campus affected the sound experience of its residents. Using “temporal

sound fixation,” significant moments in the university soundscape were captured, such as birdsong, weather phenomena, and nocturnal serenity, which evoked feelings of belonging and symbolic links to the territory. The second case dealt with an academic event focused on the development of scientific and artistic skills, where the emotions expressed by the participants were recorded and classified. From this exercise, an emotional taxonomy was constructed that included positive, negative, relational, and sensory feelings. This showed how emotional experiences affect knowledge acquisition and the formation of sensitive communities.

Finally, in the fifth phase, the findings were interpreted through data triangulation and the use of grounded theory (Glaser and Strauss, 1967). This stage allowed for the integration of voices, sounds, images, and meanings into a complex narrative about the university as a sensitive territory. The conversations focused on the importance of the senses and emotions as mediators of knowledge, the importance of creating emotionally positive environments, and the strategic role of university extension as a space for articulation between academic knowledge and social experience.

This methodological journey not only led to the creation of situated and transdisciplinary knowledge but also showed how powerful sensitivity and affection can be in modern educational processes. The senses and emotions were not just additional data, they were fundamental parts of a more humane university, connected to its environment and to the voices that inhabit it.

Literature review

This paper presents an analysis of literature in the growing field of sensory studies, covering the period 2000-2025. To identify contemporary authors, prestigious publishers were selected, and comprehensive readings were carried out in order to scan and highlight the most relevant dimensions. Based on this, a document was prepared that identifies the characters, constructs, and overall structure of each work, which facilitated its reading and understanding (see Table 1).

Table 1
Dimensions addressed by the study

Author	Document	Dimensions	Descriptions
Geurts (2002)	<i>Culture and the senses: Bodily ways of knowing in an African community</i>	Senses as cultural constructs	Geurts demonstrates that the senses are not merely a physiological experience but are culturally mediated and the product of specific knowledge systems. Sensory perception depends on the cultural values, practices, and contexts in which it develops.
		Expansion of the sensory framework	Geurts introduces the concept of “seselelame,” a term that refers to an integral bodily sense and a holistic awareness of the body in the world. This includes: The ability to feel with the whole body, beyond specific sensory organs. The recognition of emotions, intuitions, and other sensory aspects as valid forms of knowledge.
		Bodily ways of knowing	For the Anlo-Ewe community, the body acts as a vehicle for knowledge and learning, where the senses are essential tools for interacting with and understanding the environment. Sensory perception involves the physical as well as the emotional and spiritual, forming an integrated system of bodily knowledge.
Stewart (2007)	<i>Ordinary affects</i>	Affects	These are forces or intensities that are not always expressed consciously or verbally but are felt and experienced in the body and in the environment.
		Ordinary as a field of possibilities	Describes everyday life as a space in constant motion, full of open and non-linear possibilities. The ordinary is not static; it is composed of dynamics, encounters, and connections that emerge spontaneously. These moments can trigger processes of change or remain as small affective vibrations that permeate routines.
		Social tensions	Small gestures or everyday emotions can reveal broader social tensions, such as discomfort at work, consumerism, or structural inequalities. Shift the gaze to the small and subtle to recognize the emotional intensities that shape the everyday world.
Guber, (2011)	<i>Ethnographic</i>	Observation	“Observation is a qualitative research technique that allows the researcher to directly capture social facts, behaviors, and events in their natural context, providing a deeper understanding of the meanings that social actors attach to their actions” (Guber, 2011, p. 143).
		Participant observation	“Participant observation involves the researcher participating in people’s daily lives, taking on different roles, and sharing situations that allow them to understand from within” (Guber, 2011, p. 79).

Author	Document	Dimensions	Descriptions
		Unstructured observation	“Unstructured observation is flexible, open to the unexpected, and does not depend on a fixed protocol of pre-established categories” (Guber, 2011, p. 78).
		Direct observation	“This is direct, immediate observation carried out by the researcher, who is present in the situation” (Guber, 2011, p. 77).
Robert E. Stake (2000)	<i>The art of case study research</i>	Sensory-ethnographic observation	Sensory-ethnographic observation has a deep connection with the researcher’s emotional and bodily experience, becoming a complex instrument of perception that transcends mechanical or structured recording. As the following comment states: “Good observers see with their ears and listen with their eyes” (Stake, 2000, cited in Guber, 2011, p. 82).
Corbin (2005)	<i>Charting the cultural history of the senses</i>	Historicity of the senses	The senses are neither universal nor timeless but are historically conditioned. Each society and historical period organizes, hierarchizes, and values the senses in a particular way.
		Sensory experience	Each sense can be educated or disciplined to align with the demands of a specific social context.
		Senses and spatiality	The senses interact with spaces and landscapes, particularly in contexts such as the city, the countryside, or nature. The senses allow us to build a sensory relationship with our environment, shaping experiences that are both individual and collective.
		Sensory hierarchy	Throughout history, the senses have been ranked according to the dominant needs and values of each era. Sight has been predominant in Western modernity, while other senses, such as smell and touch, have been marginalized or considered inferior.
		Collective identity	Corbin explores how sensory experiences contribute to the construction of individual and collective identities. The senses participate in rituals, memories, and social practices that define a community. For example, the sound of church bells, the aromas of festivities, or the textures of everyday objects are part of the sensory imagery shared by a culture.
		Affection and sensory memory	It recognizes that the senses are deeply connected to affections and memory. Sensory experiences evoke emotions and memories that can be personal or communal. This dimension highlights how the senses contribute to shaping the past, both in individual terms (sensory memory) and in the reconstruction of cultural history.
Pink, (2015)	<i>Doing sensory ethnography</i>	Use of audiovisual media	The role of audiovisual media (photography, video, sound recordings) as complementary tools for documenting and representing sensory experiences. These resources allow recording non-textual dimensions of the field, such as sounds, movements, and atmospheres.

Author	Document	Dimensions	Descriptions
		Creation of sensory knowledge	The knowledge generated from sensory ethnography is transdisciplinary, integrating perspectives from anthropology, sociology, cultural studies, and visual arts. This knowledge not only describes people's sensory worlds, but also explores how these worlds shape identities, memories, and everyday practices.
Howes (2024)	<i>Sensory investigations: an introduction to sensory anthropology</i>	Sensory anthropology	The study of how different cultures perceive and value sensory experiences. This approach emphasizes that the senses are culturally shaped and that each society has a particular "sensory hierarchy" that influences how the world is experienced and interpreted.
		Cultural sensorium	Refers to the organized set of senses in a specific culture. Howes argues that each society configures its own sensorium, determining which senses are most valued and how they should be used in social contexts.
		Sensory relativism	Sensory experiences are not universal but vary significantly between cultures. Howes argues that what one culture may perceive as a pleasant smell, another may consider unpleasant, exemplifying how sensory perceptions are culturally conditioned.
		History of the senses	Howes explores how sensory perceptions have evolved over time and how historical changes have reconfigured sensory hierarchies in different societies. For example, he analyzes how the Industrial Revolution altered auditory and olfactory experiences in cities.
		Politics of the senses	Howes examines how sensory experiences can be subject to social regulation and control, and how power and authority can influence which senses are privileged or repressed in a given society.

Note: Prepared in accordance with open-access documents on the authors' platforms: Corbin (2005); Geurts (2002); Howes (2024); Pink (2015); Stewart (2007), cited in the growing field of sensory studies (Howes, 2014). The *scanning* technique is used, which performs a quick scan to identify keywords and their meanings. For the observation technique, the different techniques are described based on Guber (2011) and Stake (2000). In addition, underlining is used to highlight the main ideas of the text with lines and annotations.

Fieldwork

The study was carried out within the framework of the intensive summer course: *Agile and Active Management for Educational Projects with Qualitative Methods* of the Graduate Program in Teaching Specialization of the Faculty of Education, at the Autonomous University of Yucatán. Participants

were selected through direct sampling, forming a group of new-generation teachers in training, in collaboration with the authors actively involved in the development of the project.

In a participatory context, the study argues that it is essential to link relevant academic levels and teaching experience. In this regard, Durston and Miranda (2002) mention that “participatory research aims to produce knowledge by critically articulating contributions to science and popular knowledge” (p. 5). This vision facilitates not only the enhancement of local capacities, but also the alteration of social realities regarding educational needs.

Instruments

The use of ethnographic-sensory observation protocols, as well as the design of audiovisual data collection activities, helped define a specific area of research that was dynamic and situated. This area was oriented toward the analysis of educational experiences from an interdisciplinary and multisensory angle.

The ethnographic method is well known for using multiple instruments to collect information and understand social phenomena across various disciplines (Hermann *et al.* and 2011). A structural-functionalist approach was used because it emphasizes rich contextual descriptions of the cultures and educational systems being studied (Malinowski, 1973), relying primarily on participant observation. This methodological decision stems from the strengths of the framework in identifying clear patterns and salient themes based on the raw data collected in the university environment (Angrosino, 2012, p. 19).

The structural-functionalist approach, in Malinowski’s work (1973), is characterized by being holistic because it analyzes cultural interactions that are essential for social consistency and balance. Along these lines, the basic framework of the sensory-ethnographic observation protocol proposed by Stake (2000) was formulated, which combines parts such as: participant, unstructured, and direct observation, as shown in Figure 2.

For this study, Guber’s (2011) observation typologies, described in Table 1, allowed for conceptualization of their applicability through the dynamic relationships of coexistence practices and life on the university campus as part of an underlying holistic cultural system.

Participant observation facilitated the researcher’s immersion in academic and everyday events, while unstructured observation broadened access to less

predictable emerging phenomena. Direct observation focused on capturing spontaneous interactions and behavior patterns during critical moments such as campus opening and closing times and during cultural outreach events.

Figure 2
Sensory-ethnographic observation protocol

Note. Based on the notion of sensory-ethnographic observation, the data are addressed according to: (a) Opening and closing of the university campus; (b) Cultural outreach event; (c) Collection of narratives through audio recordings; (d) Visual recordings; (e) Observation stenography.

Techniques included concise transcription, visual records (photography and videography), and sound recordings through the collection of audio narratives, among others. These materials were complemented by field journals, schedules aligned with designated observation times, and scanning applications, which allowed for multisensory documentation of educational experiences.

Analyzing the audit records allowed for the application of data sonification techniques (Carnero-Sierra, 2022; Ruiz-del Olmo and Vertedor, 2016). This approach, informed by grounded theory reasoning (Glaser and Strauss, 1967; Bénard-Calva, 2016), facilitated the triangulation of the observation of emotional practices with reflection on meaning within shared university spaces.

These findings revealed indicators of social cohesion, such as feelings of belonging and the strengthening of community ties in interdisciplinary workshops and gatherings. In addition, it was documented that shared emotions, together with the perception of interaction, fostered the formation of “emotional communities,” defined as spaces of collective construction that enhance inclusivity and university identity.

This methodological approach provides information on how sensory perception, together with emotion intertwined with the structure of daily campus experience, shapes the campus not only as a physical site but also as a symbolic territory dense with converging educational, affective, and cultural practices.

From an eclectic holistic perspective on integrated culture as an interdependent system, there is an application of multiple case designs characterized in Stake (2000), which allows studying the interrelationships of the university campus between dimensions of sensory perception rooted in emotion and education. This approach demonstrated how these dimensions facilitate social cohesion and community inclusion by perceiving the university as an interconnected cultural system where each component helps maintain balance within the learning ecosystem.

Visual data is addressed according to how participants generate images through photographs that represent their experiences, called windows, allowing for the exploration of personal and cultural meanings attributed to the images (Mannay, 2015). With the collection of this data, a critical and reflective analysis of the photographs produced by the participants is generated. For Banks (2010), at the moment of image creation, when the social researcher takes out their camera and begins to film or take photographs, they must know enough about the community in accordance with their research, emphasizing the observational analysis of images in the context of production, interpretation, and use of photographs from a legal-ethical framework (p. 119).

The visual data collection technique consisted of asking participants for images that described three moments in the territory based on a memorable memory, a meaningful learning experience, and a conflict (see Table 2).

Table 2
Visual data recording

Window	Reflective analysis
	<p>Important memory: Third-floor terrace. ... “The third-floor terrace is a quiet place where you can think, rest, and even reflect, as it is quite peaceful and cool. It reminds me of important moments when, between class breaks, I would go up to watch the sunsets. This allowed me to rest and take a breath before continuing with the heavy workload of some days.”</p>
	<p>Meaningful learning: Tables in the garden on the ground floor ... “Under the umbrella of one of those tables, we concluded our work on educational psychology, a blog recorded by each of the members at different points during the course, and we gathered here to make the final recording. For me, it is significant because in that video we gathered everything that each of us had learned, and it was interesting to listen to and find out what each of us learned from that wonderful course.”</p>

Note. Narrative description by the participant.

Historical-geographical context

The history of the Faculty of Education at the Autonomous University of Yucatán shows a process of institutional strengthening focused on academic reinforcement and the decentralization of education. Since it began in 1977 as an assembly resulting from an agreement with the UNAM, innovative programs such as the Specialization in Teaching and the Master’s Degree in Hig-

her Education (Maestría en Educación Superior) were promoted. In 1984, it was established as a faculty, which represented a turning point with the introduction of the bachelor's degree in education. Over the course of forty years, it has stood out for expanding its reach, such as with the Multidisciplinary Unit in Tizimín, and for continuously renewing its plans and programs, including varied modalities and quality criteria. The perspective of teacher training with a reflective, ethical, and inclusive approach has guided its evolution. Currently, decision-makers have converged on schools of thought such as the Chicago School and the Ibero-American vision; the Faculty maintains a robust educational proposal and a commitment to educational change in the region.

The Faculty of Education is located on the Social Sciences, Economics, Administration, and Humanities Campus of the Autonomous University of Yucatán. Its design reflects a perspective of integration between the natural environment and academic work, honoring the endemic vegetation and more than 300 mature trees of the original jungle environment. The spaces were designed not only for transit and educational activity, but also to promote reflection, gathering, and team learning.

The center of the campus, a 1,300 m² green plaza, acts as a symbolic and operational hub connecting the different academic and administrative sectors, reinforcing the institution's identity and sense of community. This architectural layout meets the demands of a modern university that aspires to educate professionals who interact with their territory and cultural environment (Departamento de Proyectos de la Facultad de Arquitectura, 2018).

Data analysis

Qualitative data analysis (QDA) in the research allowed us to understand the social phenomenon from the university campus by identifying patterns and behavior of the groups for the development of the categorization system (coding) from a deductive approach. It should be noted that Schreier (2012) mentions that QCA (*Qualitative Content Analysis*) is a method for systematically describing the broad meaning of qualitative material. It is performed by manually classifying the material as instances of the categories of a coding framework.

According to Gibbs (2022), "codes provide a focus for thinking about the text and its interpretation." (p. 66). This key function records the development of ideas for the analysis of qualitative data. Using digital processes, the transcripts of the audio narratives were analyzed, and the images recor-

ded through the participatory method were identified to generate categories and subcategories based on relevant qualities. These codes, called patterns, follow a round process to refine the coding system, allowing the data to be visualized and the results to be explored using MAXQDA2024 software. This process allows the research questions and hypotheses to be answered, as well as the relationships between the ideas in the analysis to be visualized (Kuckartz and Rädiker, 2023).

With the identification of the categorization system (coding) from the deductive approach, 20,691 open codes were identified, based on the narrative, visual, and audio data from the data collection. With inductive coding, 243 codes were selected, of which only 40 codes are addressed for the study (see Figure 3).

Figure 3

Frequency of open coding based on narrative, visual, and audio data

Note: The color shows the sum of the frequency, calculated using the online software tableau.com.

Table 3 organizes the levels of analysis of ethnographic-sensory study into three interrelated scales: micro, meso, and macro. This framework allows for a systematic understanding of sensory and emotional experiences on the university campus, placing them within broader and more abstract theoretical, social, and spatial frameworks.

At the micro level, there is concrete evidence from fieldwork, such as gestures, perceptions, memories involving the senses, and emotions. This level demonstrates some aspects of the emotional dynamics in everyday life among educators.

The meso level presents a theoretical context with key researchers, guiding research questions, qualitative methodologies that support the analysis, and its framing components. Consideration is also visible as a cross-cutting approach along with ethnographic observation and event sampling techniques.

Finally, the macro level integrates these experiences into broader socio-cultural structures such as: city, contemporary society, gender theory, politics, urban studies, and sensitivity. In this case, it situates phenomena at the regional or global level while interpreting the relationships between territory, body, and knowledge. Therefore, the table facilitates the interpretation of the sensory phenomenon in a university setting from a transdisciplinary and multi-scalar situated perspective.

Table 3
Dimensions of the study from the micro, meso, and macro perspectives

Micro	Meso	Macro
Learning	Post-phenomenological	City
	Sensory sociability	Street
	Contemporary society	University
	Sociology	
Counting	Gestures	
	Tactile invasion	
	Sensory memory	
	Perception	
	Perception of the senses	
	Sensitive proximity	
Believing	Expressions	
Question	Space	World
Emotion	Affectivity	Central America
Understand	Narrative ability	
	Natural sensory certainty	
	Five senses	
	Power issues	

Experience	Alain Corbin	Time
	Brian Massumi	
	David Howes	
	Georg Simmel	
	Gilles Deleuze	
	Howard Becker	
	Jonathan H. Turner	
	Kathleen Stewart	
	Kathryn Linn Geurts	
	Kolen Hymen	
	Sarah Pink	
Talk	Sensory Turn	
	Shared vocabulary	
Thinking	How is the sensory ethnography method carried out?	Qualitative research
	What is the relationship between the sensory turn and the contemporary digital condition from an auditory and visual perspective?	Sensory-ethnographic observation
	What are the methodologies for studying the senses in ethnographic contexts?	Event sampling
	Is the sensory turn related to phenomenological studies?	Multiple cases
Perception	Taxonomy of emotions	
Feeling	Sociological spirit	Theory of sensitivity
		Theory of gender
		Theory of urbanism
		Political theory
Signify	Sensory workshops	
Dream	Sensory experiences	Jungle songs Weather phenomenon Nocturnal serenity

Note. Macro, environment within which the problem or area of research exists; Meso, contextualization of the problem in the subarea where it is theoretically inserted; Micro, explains how the problem manifests itself, indicating objective evidence through narratives, videos, and photographs. It is the microenvironment where the data emerges.

Results

Case 1: University context

The natural landscape and the ancient identity of the Mayan population refer to a connection with the territory, history, culture, and pre-Hispanic traditions, which remain valid over time. It is considered an ancient identity because of its roots that go back thousands of years in the Mesoamerican territory. In modern times, Mérida, Yucatán continues to be a capital of active megaprojects within the context of the Maya Zone, with possibilities for water supply, a direct relationship with natural resources, and construction stones that emerge from the Yucatán Peninsula, as described by Franco-Cáceres (2021). Our research context is located on the Mérida-Motul highway, kilometer 1, in Gran San Pedro Cholul; the university campus is located in the Mayan Jungle, embracing a large courtyard that contains multiple atmospheres: 1) a three-level orthogonal body for educational classrooms; 2) a two-level triangle for administrators and research cubicles; 3) two curved volumes for administration and services (Faculty of Education of the Autonomous University of Yucatán, 2018). To actively focus the university campus on the territory, three sensory experiences are addressed, focusing on auditory and visual temporal fixation, called: (1) Songs of the jungle; (2) Meteorological phenomenon; and (3) Nocturnal serenity.

To actively focus the university campus on the territory, three moments are addressed, focusing on auditory fixation in time, called: Jungle songs; Meteorological phenomenon; and Nocturnal serenity (Table 4).

Table 4
Selection of auditory temporal fixation

Dimension	Total duration	Schedule	Time		Description of the fixation temporal auditory
			E	S	
Opening: Time 01	24:00:00	08:30:00	00:01:26	00:02:02	Jungle sounds: Birds Whispers of students: Classrooms
Moment 02		05:30:00	00:01:33	00:01:42	Storm: Weather phenomenon
Closing: Moment 03		09:00:00	00:00:00	00:00:00	Serenity: When the sun sets and night begins.

Note: Own elaboration; the abbreviations “E” refers to the entry and “S” to the exit of the sound according to the time marking.

In line with the above, Heidegger (1947), in his work *Letter on Humanism*, highlights that “language is the home of being,” emphasizing that language is not only a construction but also the soul of humanity. Through it, heaven and earth are intertwined, which is a relevant allegory for identifying the narratives of the territory. In this sense, the relationship between the educational center and its natural environment is explored as a complex and dynamic ecosystem (Murillo-García, 2022). In this space, living beings interact in a social and natural environment, generating bidirectional processes of knowledge from their daily lives. Here, the environment acts as a regulator of the emotional, cognitive, social, and physical.

In the context of the university campus in the Mayan area, the natural environment is clear in the audio recordings captured at 08:30:00 [Moment 01]. For example, in the audio chain between 00:01:26 and 00:02:02, entitled *Songs of the jungle and birds, murmurs of students in classrooms*, geographical aspects such as the landscape, climate, fauna, and flora can be perceived. This ecosystem, characterized by a sub-humid environment due to precipitation, generates ambient humidity that retains heat, causing low temperatures and facilitating the life of larger fauna in cool environments. The vocalization effect of birds is noticeable, a phenomenon in which birdsong invokes rain, marks territory, and maintains contact with other members of the species.

To learn more about the sounds of the peninsular ecosystem, we recommend consulting Garrido-Ávila (2020), who identifies key terms in the *Mayan Glossary*: *K'ÍINIL* (sounds of the weather), *CHÚUN LU'UM* (subsoil sounds), *U WICH LU'UM* (soil sounds), and *JA'* (water sounds). These references are essential for understanding the ecological environment of the context studied.

In addition, the use of technology played a key role in the data collection process. Technological tools such as *Merlin Bird ID*, developed by the *Cornell Lab of Ornithology*, made it possible to capture and analyze the environmental sounds of the university context.

This application, supported by repositories such as the *Macaulay Library* and *eBird*, converts sounds into spectrograms, three-dimensional representations that associate sound signals with bird species. In this way, technology facilitated the evocation of sensory perception, promoting the creation of new knowledge by stimulating auditory curiosity. This is particularly relevant in the habitat of migratory birds that coexist in the rainforest introduced on the university campus.

In conclusion, this integration offers a transdisciplinary approach that strengthens environmental and social awareness in the university community. Through observation of the environment and analysis of its sounds and images, the aim was to develop an emotional and sensory connection with the landscape, creating an atmosphere that promotes the formation of citizens in an environment of sustainability.

Case 2: Campus in motion

The campus in motion manifests as a narrative structure established in the recognition of emotions during the event “Skills in science and arts in agile management for educational projects with qualitative methods”, held on the university campus. This event fostered a social dialogue with the university community (composed of parents, administrative staff, teachers, among others) aimed at developing scientific dissemination processes to enhance teaching specialization skills within a graduate program.

During the event, fifteen topics were presented by the participants, following a sequential cascade format. This structure facilitated audience comprehension, resulting in a link between behavior and cognitive experiences. These records made it possible to identify the emotions of the participants as they expressed their experiences with the environment through narratives.

Taxonomy of emotions

- Positive emotions: these emotions are related to rewarding experiences in the teaching-learning process and interaction with students and colleagues, based on:
 - ✓ Satisfaction: participants express their contentment and satisfaction with the experience. For example, one individual states: “I am very happy to participate in this experience.”
 - ✓ Motivation: An intense sense of enthusiasm is evident, particularly regarding learning and improving skills. One subject notes that they have improved their teaching skills and feel “better prepared” and “eager to continue learning.”

- ✓ Appreciation: the workshop's approach and the instructor's passion are appreciated, providing a nourishing and creative experience for participants.
- ✓ Curiosity and desire to acquire knowledge: Some participants express a desire to acquire new knowledge and be at the forefront of their discipline, demonstrating a positive attitude toward personal and professional development. Another mentioned the sense that it enhanced: "A very visual, colorful experience that we don't usually have here, and in the end, it resulted in a well-structured, elaborate academic product."
- Negative emotions: These emotions arise from obstacles, administrative pressures, tense relationships, or situations of failure.
 - ✓ Frustration: occurs when there are barriers that prevent the expected performance. In the case of one participant, gestures and tone of voice were compared when mentioning their positive experience (which was negative).
 - ✓ Anxiety: derived from the pressure to meet educational quality standards and external evaluations, participants felt pressure a few days before their presentation and accreditation of the event.
 - ✓ Anger: caused by conflicts in academic or administrative dynamics, based on unilateral decision-making in educational and administrative policies.
- Relational emotions: linked to human interactions in the university context, nature, and community building.
 - ✓ Affection: development of emotional bonds with students or colleagues, fostering a collaborative environment. Participants felt connected to a group working on a joint project. One participant mentioned: "I was really happy because since the specialization began, this is the first time I feel that we are working on something focused on my area, which is part of the arts, so I am very happy, I feel comfortable with the work completed, and I would like to continue participating in this type of activity."
 - ✓ Commitment: emotional responsibility for students' well-being and academic success. Constant support for participants when they face academic difficulties.

- ✓ Trust: a feeling of security and mutual support in relationships, according to one participant's comment: "Good teachers, but those who put love, perseverance, and motivation in their work are the ones who have good teaching practices."
- ✓ Disappointment: negative perception due to unmet expectations in the project presented.
- Sensory emotions, which arise through sensory experiences linked to the physical and relational environment of the university.
 - ✓ Fulfilment: emotional balance achieved in an environment that positively stimulates the senses. This data was obtained from the event's guest book, which contained positive messages from the university community.

The implications of our study's results allow us to identify the sensory shift and phenomenological studies integrated through case studies: (1) University campus context, (2) Campus in motion. These are described below:

For case 1, it allows for a deep understanding of the natural environment based on sensory experience. While the sensory turn emphasizes the importance of the senses, phenomenology provides a method for describing and analyzing these experiences, highlighting how individuals experience and attribute meaning to the territory. In this context, the auditory and visual perception of the university campus not only documents sounds and landscapes, but also allows to explore how these sensory experiences strengthen the emotional and cultural connection with the environment, promoting environmental awareness and territorial identity, as confirmed by the comment: "...Watching the sunsets allowed me to rest and take a break to continue with the load of some days." [Participant].

Moving forward in our reasoning, emotions and senses emerge as vehicles of knowledge that connect the university community with its natural territory. Through case 2, transdisciplinarity as a product of emotions and senses in motion allows us to identify the integration of emotions and senses in a social dialogue during activities presented at the "Skills in Science and Arts" event, promoting a transdisciplinary perspective in the following terms.

Figure 4
Taxonomy of emotions

Note: The figure presents a taxonomy of emotions identified through ethnographic-sensory studies, representing them based on visual data, audio recordings, and narratives from participants. Emotions are divided into four categories: positive, negative, relational, and sensory. This classification helps to understand the impact of the physical context, along with community interactions in academia, since it shapes and defines the emotional experience of educational actors in university settings.

The promotion of collaboration is identified, because relational emotions (affection, commitment, trust) allow individuals to overcome disciplinary

barriers and work as a team, generating shared knowledge and an integrated vision. In turn, the reinterpretation of the environment, based on interaction with the territory and sensory stimulation, connects nature, culture, and knowledge, facilitating critical reflection and the development of proposals aimed at sustainability and social innovation. The movement through the dialogue of knowledge, fostered in an emotionally positive and sensorially stimulating environment, favors the convergence of different areas of knowledge (sciences, arts, and humanities), allowing for a holistic approach to addressing complex problems.

The theoretical basis identified in the study is based on sensitivity theory, gender theory, urbanism theory, and political theory. These allow us to make the following assertions:

Architecture, urban planning, and the design of public spaces (Harvey, 2008; Lefebvre, 1991) play a key role in how people perceive and relate to their environment. These spaces create experiences of power, control, and segregation, and public universities can use different areas of management to favorably influence environments from a sensory perspective. Through gender roles (Butler, 1990) and sensory perception: the way people experience the world sensorially is influenced by gender norms. At our event, women were more sensitive to certain stimuli—such as the scent of flowers or the texture and decoration of the venue—than men, while hegemonic masculinities tend to reject certain forms of sensitivity (Merleau-Ponty, 1945).

Merleau-Ponty's theory of sensitivity (1945) addresses the importance of emotions and sensory perception in the constitution of the subject and society. This theory is closely connected to phenomenology, psychology, and aesthetics (Scheler, 1954; Shusterman, 1992). With the design of sensory experiences as knowledge, sensitivity emerges as the primary form of access to the world. Sensory perception is not only a physical response to stimuli, but also a form of subjective and emotional knowledge.

It should be noted that educational processes must be marked by empathy and affection, since emotional sensitivity is closely linked to empathy and the way emotions are transmitted sensorially between people. For example, affective experiences are strengthened when teachers manage to identify their students' motivation, shaping the relationship with others through bilateral perception.

To conclude this section, we consider that sensory theory is not only an approach focused on the senses, but a complex way of examining the social world and its structures. Each of these perspectives offers a unique lens for understanding how sensory experiences affect identity, power (Bourdieu, 1979; Gramsci, 1971; Foucault, 1975), culture, and resistance.

Public administration geared toward social participation in university outreach areas can foster the formation of sensitive and inclusive communities through various strategies and approaches that emanate from the sensory approach in sociology. This methodology facilitates understanding of how sensory experiences and emotions affect the way individuals interact with each other and their environment. This is how we identify that proximity sensitivity posits that when individuals share a space, their bodies perceive each other through the senses, generating a reciprocal impact, both in the sensory and emotional spheres.

This has the potential to promote a sense of community and connection between individuals, an essential aspect for the formation of inclusive communities. Furthermore, it is important to note that interaction, managed at the university, can foster interactions that transcend cognitive and emotional dimensions, thus facilitating sensory and emotional interactions. The establishment of spaces where individuals can exchange their experiences and emotions fosters a culture of empathy and understanding, which are fundamental aspects for the development of sensitive communities.

It should be noted that the generation of collective narratives through social participation facilitates active listening of diverse individuals. This not only enhances the community but also contributes to the identification of inequalities and action aimed at overcoming them.

Understanding inclusive methodologies, from the post-phenomenological movement and the use of technology, can favor ethnographic research. The implementation of methodologies that consider the heterogeneity of participants' sensory and emotional experiences can be fundamental to the advancement of the line of research. In addition, it is necessary to relate to literary, aesthetic, and poetic narratives from the creation of sensitive environments.

Figure 5
Conceptual and systematic cartography of the posthuman phenomenon

Note. The image represents a conceptual and systematic cartography of the posthuman phenomenon, considering four interconnected dimensions: explanatory theories of sensitivity, gender, urbanism, and inclusive politics (post-phenomenological theory) that include methods such as qualitative research and sensory ethnography; sensory research that integrates body, affect, and territory; the construction of meanings through embodiment and corporeality in educational practices. This structure makes it possible to understand posthumanism in educational contexts based on affective, political, and community configurations that give visibility to modes of existence, learning, and relationships from a multisensory and relational perspective.

Conclusions and discussion

It is concluded that the contributions of Bourdieu, Foucault, Gramsci, and Merleau-Ponty to the field of education allow us to understand that the construction of knowledge, power, the body, culture, and hegemony in school and social spaces should not be assumed to be neutral or natural realities. On the contrary, it is necessary to denaturalize them and analyze them critically from their political, social, and symbolic dimensions.

The analysis of the participants' photographs showed how certain spaces shape power through practices of surveillance, normalization, and disciplining of the body. These findings allow us to understand education as a device of power-knowledge, where knowledge is linked to relations of domination that produce subjectivities that are obedient and functional to the social order.

Thus, it is essential to recognize that education cannot be reduced to the purely cognitive, but rather manifests itself as an embodied, corporeal experience situated in an intersubjective world. This understanding makes it possible to move toward sensitive pedagogical approaches, where the body and the senses play an essential role in the learning process.

From Gramsci's perspective, school is a space of ideological fight between projects of hegemony. In contrast to the traditional model that reproduces the dominant order, he proposes an education for emancipation articulated with social movements and popular sectors. This critique of traditional education is relevant in the context of posthumanist thought, considering the relationships between education, nature, and territory.

The affective studies addressed in this research offer an interdisciplinary field on the role of emotions, affects, and intensities in social, political, and educational life. From this perspective, emphasis is placed on how relational, bodily, and sociocultural practices are experienced in an embodied way and situated in specific contexts, allowing for a more sensitive and complex reading of educational processes.

Authors such as Brian Massumi, David Howes, Kathleen Stewart, Sara Ahmed, and Sarah Pink have made fundamental contributions to the field of education by highlighting the importance of embodied learning, the design of sensitive pedagogical experiences, and attention to the affective intensities that shape subjectivities. From their approaches, it is recognized that every day, the body, and sensory are key dimensions for understanding how meanings are generated in educational contexts.

In dialogue with the Chicago School and its emphasis on situated methodologies, it is essential to affirm that all truth is local, constructed relationally, and conditioned by the specific contexts of knowledge production and validation. Within this framework, the phenomenon of post-truth is transformed according to the pedagogical tactics that teachers adopt from their environment, highlighting the role of geographical territory and the natural environment in shaping educational processes.

In this process, emotions emerge through a taxonomy as an epistemic mediator, forming part of power structures that regulate actions, relationships, discourses, and events. Thus, emotions shape behaviors, define school climates, and configure contexts with epistemic authority where the emotional occupies a central place.

The course “Agile and Active Management for Educational Projects with Qualitative Methods” allowed us to identify the effects of the natural and urban environments, which condition the way emotions and senses are experienced, interpreted, and shared within the educational context. These spaces are not only physical settings but also affective contexts that shape the perception, concentration, well-being, and creativity of those who participate. The presence of green spaces, air quality, noise, architecture, and spatial layout directly influence the sensory and emotional experiences of faculty and students. Likewise, the interaction between nature and the city is reflected in everyday practices of knowledge, such as walking around campus, observing the environment, stopping to listen, or feeling the weather. These experiences have an impact on the formation of subjectivities and the construction of knowledge, as they mobilize memories, desires, tensions, and affections that connect the academic with the vital, the individual with the collective.

From a posthuman perspective, we must ask ourselves: what does this *quantum* require in contemporary teacher training? This question prompts an in-depth analysis of the current meanings of educational leadership and teacher development, recognizing epistemic, cultural, and narrative diversity with fundamental axes. Based on the Chicago School, an intercultural, decolonial, and transdisciplinary discussion is promoted, which questions the hierarchies of traditional knowledge and favors the emergence of new teaching skills.

In this framework, the philosophical quantum manifests itself as situated knowledge, guided by a reflective and ethical approach to analysis. This implies recognizing the direct involvement of the teacher-researcher in the

process of creating new knowledge, emphasizing the importance of teachers understanding their territory and the places where learning experiences take place. In addition, their participation in academic life is perceived through the cultural context, and the joint creation of knowledge with communities is promoted, overcoming the logic of intervention in them.

This involves the use of qualitative methods that enable people to express their experiences in a more comprehensive manner, which could lead to an increased sense of belonging and active participation in the community. For public administration at the university, understood as the ability to articulate meaningful links with various social actors, it is essential to promote social participation and the formation of sensitive and inclusive communities.

This management should not be reduced to strategies for outreach or audience training, but should be oriented toward the creation of dialogical, affective, and ethical spaces where the voices, knowledge, and experiences of students, teachers, local communities, and external actors are recognized and valued. Communities are formed through forums, collaborative projects, artistic activities, interventions in the territory, and social responsibility actions, not only sharing academic objectives but also emotional and political commitments to equity, social justice, and the common good. This approach builds bridges between the university and its surroundings, as well as between universities through the pedagogy of encounter and mutual recognition.

In conclusion, this research contributes to the field of education by highlighting the relevance of a situated, affective, and transdisciplinary pedagogy. Its findings can serve as a basis for future research on teacher well-being and sensory and ethnographic methodologies in higher education, especially in the social sciences, humanities, and economic-administrative disciplines.

References

- Ahmed, S. (2015). *La política cultural de las emociones*. Programa Universitario de Estudios de Género, Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México. <https://bit.ly/3VOjoma>
- Angrosino, M. (2012). *Etnografía y observación participante en investigación cualitativa*. Ediciones Morata. <https://bit.ly/3P2Ku5g>
- Báez, F. (2023). Un pasito aquí y un pasito allá: Relación musical entre Centroamérica y el Caribe. En N. García-Sánchez (coord.), *Centroamérica, Revista de la Universidad de México* (pp. 14-19). Cultura UNAM. <https://bit.ly/3ZSfFFM>

- Banks, M. (2010). *Los datos visuales en investigación cualitativa*. Morata. <https://bit.ly/44DE6Kr>
- Bénard-Calva, S. (2016). *La teoría fundamentada: Una metodología cualitativa*. Universidad Autónoma de Aguascalientes. <https://bit.ly/49K0T8e>
- Bolaños Florido, L. P. (2015). El estudio sociohistórico de las emociones y los sentimientos en las Ciencias Sociales del siglo XX. *Revista de Estudios Sociales*, 1(55), 178-191. <https://doi.org/10.7440/res55.2016.12>
- Bourdieu, P. (1979). *La distinción: Criterio y bases sociales del juicio*. Ediciones Siglo XXI. <https://bit.ly/3BDeyBz>
- Bourdin, G. L. (2016). Antropología de las emociones: conceptos y tendencias. *Cuicuilco Revista de Ciencias Antropológicas*, 23(67), 55-74. <https://bit.ly/4frpaBp>
- Butler, J. (1990). *Gender trouble: Feminism and the subversion of identity*. Routledge. <https://bit.ly/4fskICj>
- Carnero-Sierra, S. (2022). La sonificación como herramienta en Psicología. *Revista Electrónica de Metodología Aplicada*, 24(2), 31-44. <https://doi.org/10.17811/rem.24.2.2022.31-44>
- Castro, E. (2014). *Introducción a Foucault*. Siglo XXI. <https://bit.ly/4gGiBMj>
- Castro, S. (2010). *Historia de la gubernamentalidad. Razón de Estado, liberalismo y neoliberalismo en Michel Foucault*. Pontificia Universidad Javeriana. <https://bit.ly/4guLnQj>
- Collins, R. (1975). *Conflict sociology: Toward an explanatory science*. Academic Press. <https://bit.ly/49KP1ms>
- Corbin, A. (2005). *Charting the cultural history of the senses*. En C. Classen (ed.), *The Book of Touch* (pp. 128-135). Berg Publishers. <https://bit.ly/3Bsc8pv>
- Deleuze, G. (2015). *La subjetivación. Curso sobre Foucault*. Cactus. <https://bit.ly/4gEeC3r>
- Deleuze, G. and Guattari, F. (1987). *A thousand plateaus: Capitalism and schizophrenia* (B. Massumi, trans.). University of Minnesota Press. <https://bit.ly/4gpuPsP>
- Denzin, N. and Lincoln, Y. (1998). *Handbook of Qualitative Research*. Sage Publications. <https://bit.ly/4fuENb4>
- Denzin, N. and Lincoln, Y. (2012). *Manual de investigación cualitativa: El campo de la investigación cualitativa* (Vol. I). Editorial Gedisa. <http://bit.ly/46fdsJ1>
- Departamento de Proyectos de la Facultad de Arquitectura. (2018). *Facultad de Educación de la Universidad Autónoma de Yucatán* [blog en línea]. ArchDaily México. <https://bit.ly/3G6vbrI>

- Dreyfus, H. and Rabinow, P. (2001). *Michel Foucault: más allá del estructuralismo y la hermenéutica*. Nueva Visión. <https://bit.ly/4gK379Z>
- Durston, J. and Miranda, F. (2002). *Experiencias y metodología de la investigación participativa*. Naciones Unidas. <https://bit.ly/44CkuGu>
- Eribon, D. (1995). *Michel Foucault y sus contemporáneos*. Letra e. <https://bit.ly/4kfCB9T>
- Facultad de Educación de la Universidad Autónoma de Yucatán. (2018, 01 de mayo). *Departamento de Proyectos de la Facultad de Arquitectura* [Blog en línea]. UADY. <https://bit.ly/3ZDGQUw>
- Fernández Poncela, A. and M. (2011). Antropología de las emociones y teoría de los sentimientos. *Revista Versión Nueva Época*, 26(1),1-24. <https://bit.ly/400VYwE>
- Foucault, M. (1975). *Discipline and punish: The birth of the prison*. Pantheon Books. <https://bit.ly/3BBqG68>
- Franco-Cáceres, I. (2021). La transición de un territorio prehispánico a tierra de megaproyectos: El caso de la península de Yucatán. *Antrópica. Revista de Ciencias Sociales y Humanidades*, 7(7), 343-402. <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6863-7716>
- Garrido-Ávila, P. A. (2020). *La península de Yucatán y su entorno ecológico: con glosario en maya, náhuatl y español*. Universidad Autónoma de Yucatán. <https://bit.ly/3BqEz7e>
- Geurts, K. L. (2002). *Culture and the senses: Bodily ways of knowing in an African community*. University of California Press. <https://bit.ly/3ZRUTGi>
- Gibbs, G. (2022). *El análisis de datos cualitativos en investigación cualitativa*. Morata. <https://bit.ly/3I6CHmR>
- Glaser, B. G. and Strauss, A. L. (1967). *The discovery of grounded theory: Strategies for qualitative research*. Aldine Publishing Company. <https://bit.ly/41Jc7YF>
- Gramsci, A. (1971). *Selections from the prison notebooks*. Lawrence & Wishart. <https://bit.ly/4033yXD>
- Guber, R. (2011). Los enfoques cualitativos en la investigación en ciencias sociales. En R. Guber (ed.), *La etnografía. Método, campo y reflexividad* (pp. 135-160). Siglo XXI Editores. <https://bit.ly/44ExRWM>
- Hall, S. (1980). Cultural studies and the study of popular culture. In J. Storey (ed.), *Cultural theory and popular culture: A reader* (pp. 128-139). Routledge. <https://bit.ly/49LloBs>
- Harvey, D. (2008). *Social justice and the city*. University of Georgia Press. <https://bit.ly/3Dmi57I>

- Heidegger, M. (1947). *Carta sobre el humanismo*. Alianza editorial. <https://bit.ly/4ftaWzK>
- Heise, D. R. (1979). *Understanding events: Affect and the construction of social action*. Cambridge University Press. <https://bit.ly/49Lv4Mq>
- Hermann, T. and Hunt, A. y Neuhoff, J. G. (2011). *The sonification handbook*. Logos Verlag. <https://bit.ly/4gnsUoC>
- Hochschild, A. R. (1975). The sociology of emotions: Selected possibilities. En M. Millman y R. M. Kanter (eds.), *Another voice* (pp. 280-307). Anchor Press.
- Hochschild, A. R. (1979). Emotion work, feeling rules, and social structure. *American Journal of Sociology*, 85(3), 551-575. <https://bit.ly/45O7f6T>
- Howes, D. (2003). *Sensual relations: Engaging the senses in culture and social theory*. University of Michigan Press. <https://bit.ly/4iDAAES>
- Howes, D. (2013). *The expanding field of sensory studies* [Blog online]. Sensory studies. <https://bit.ly/3P0AGJg>
- Howes, D. (2014). El creciente campo de los estudios sensoriales. *Revista Latinoamericana de Estudios sobre Cuerpos, Emociones y Sociedad*, 6(15), 10-26. <https://bit.ly/401fwAN>
- Howes, D. (2024). *Sensory investigations: an introduction to sensory anthropology*. Pennsylvania State University Press. <https://bit.ly/3ZO2JAM>
- Jambet, Ch. (1999). Constitución del sujeto y práctica espiritual. Observaciones sobre la Historia de la sexualidad. En Balbier, E. (et al.), *Michel Foucault, filósofo*. (pp. 227-241). Gedisa.
- Jiménez-León, R. and Cisneros-Chacón, E. (2025). *Evolución de la investigación cualitativa* [Presentación de diapositivas]. Universidad Autónoma de Yucatán. <https://bit.ly/4no2FTf>
- Jiménez-León, R. and Cisneros-Chacón, E. and Paz-Reyes, J. J. y Canto-Herrera, P. (2024). *Expresiones y relatos de docentes*. Universidad Juárez Autónoma de Tabasco. <https://bit.ly/3GIYCWA>
- Kemper, T. D. (1978a). *A social interactional theory of emotions*. Wiley. <https://bit.ly/3P7Y5IK>
- Kemper, T. and D. (1978b). Toward a sociology of emotions: Some problems and some solutions. *The American Sociologist*, 13(1), 30-41. <https://bit.ly/3P6k6HL>
- Kuckartz, U. and Rädiker, S. (2023). *Qualitative Content Analysis: Methods, Practice and Software*. Sage Publications. <https://bit.ly/3P7Y1su>
- Lefebvre, H. (1991). *The production of space*. Blackwell. <https://bit.ly/4fnZTYV>
- López-Sánchez, O. (2023). Los giros del giro afectivo: la centralidad de la vida sensible para teorizar lo social: una lectura en clave latinoamericana. *Historia y Grafía*, (62), 463-301. <https://doi.org/10.48102/hyg.vi62.497>

- Malinowski, B. (1973). *Introducción: Objeto, método y finalidad de esta investigación, en Los Argonautas del Pacífico Occidental*. Península <https://bit.ly/3ZHLPU5>
- Mannay, D. (2015). *Visual, narrative and creative research methods: application, reflection, and ethics*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315775760>
- Martínez, A. (2023). Noticia de un no-lugar. En N. García-Sánchez (coord.), *Centroamérica, Revista de la Universidad de México*, 895 (pp. 105-110). CulturaUNAM. <https://bit.ly/4gJKliW>
- Massumi, B. (1995). The autonomy of affect. *Cultural Critique*, 31, 83-109. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1354446>
- Mateos-Cortés, L. S. (coord.). *Estudios interculturales desde Veracruz: Metodologías emergentes de investigación, docencia y vinculación* (pp. 121-146). Corpus Universitario. <https://bit.ly/44icWre>
- Merleau-Ponty, M. (1945). *Phenomenology of perception*. Routledge. <https://bit.ly/3P4mgaP>
- Morey, M. (2014). *Escritos sobre Foucault*. Sexto piso. <https://bit.ly/3Dt4wUb>
- Murillo-García, J. L. (2022). Monográfico: La relación entre la escuela y el entorno social y natural. *Fórum Aragón*, 35(1), 5-8. <https://bit.ly/404ayUf>
- Pink, S. (2009). *Doing sensory ethnography*. Sage Publications.
- Pink, S. (2015). *Doing sensory ethnography* (2ed). Sage Publications. <https://bit.ly/3ZM6vKJ>
- Ruiz-del Olmo, F. J. and Vertedor, J. (2016). *Procesos, herramientas y prácticas de la sonificación*. Universidad de Málaga. <https://bit.ly/4gEwuKS>
- Scheff, T. J. (1979). *Catharsis in heading, ritual, and drama*. University of California Press. <https://bit.ly/4fuuKTJ>
- Scheler, M. (1954). *The formalism in ethics and non-formal ethics of values*. Northwestern University Press. <https://bit.ly/403qYw4>
- Schreier, M. (2012). *Qualitative Content Analysis in Practice*. Sage Publications. <https://bit.ly/3Dp61Tn>
- Shusterman, R. (1992). *Pragmatist aesthetics: Living beauty, rethinking art*. Blackwell. <https://bit.ly/400GsRg>
- Stake, R. E. (2000). Case Studies. En N. K. Denzin y Y. S. Lincoln (ed.), *Handbook of Qualitative Research* (pp. 435-454). Sage. <https://bit.ly/3Dt4mw3>
- Stewart, K. (2007). *Ordinary affects*. Duke University. Press. <https://bit.ly/3P3AMj5>
- Surrallés, A. (1998). Entre el pensar y el sentir. La antropología frente a las emociones. *Anthropologica*, 16(16),291-304. <https://doi.org/10.18800/anthropologica.199801.013>

- Turner, J. H. (2009). The sociology of emotions: basic theoretical arguments. *Emotion Review*, 1(4), 340-354. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1754073909338305>
- Williams, R. (1977). *Marxism and literature*. Oxford University Press. <https://bit.ly/49MY3PU>

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Declaration on the Use of Artificial Intelligence
The authors DECLARE that the preparation of the article <i>Territory, senses, and emotions: a transdisciplinary case study of the university campus</i> did not use Artificial Intelligence (AI).